

H1.1 MS EAA S P K K V A P K K K P A A K K T A D H P K **Y V D M I K A A I A T L K E R G G** S S R Q A I T K **Y I H A N Y K V A E N** S D H H L K M A L K **R G V T S G D L I Q T K** G T G A S G S F K L G Q V K K E K P K K V A A K K P T A K K P A A K K S T P K K K A A K K S T P K K A A K K P A A K K A S A K K P A A K K P T K K P V A K K P A A K K V K K T P K K A K K T A K K
H1.2 M V A A K K N A D H P L F I E M I S A A **I T A L K** E R K G S S R Q A I V K Y I K **A N Y K V G D N V E T V V K** M T L K R N I G - G R L V Q T K G T G A S G S F K L S A P A A K K P - - - - A A K K P A A K K P A A K K A V A K K P S A K K - T P K K T T T - - - A T K K K T P K K A A K K T P T K K S P A K K A V K K S K A K K T P T K K S K K
H2A.1 M S G R G K G G K A K A K A K T R **S S R A G L Q F P V G R V H R** F L R - R G H Y A N R I G S G A P V Y L A A V L E Y L S A E I L E L A G N A A R D N K K A R I I P R **H L Q L A V R** N D E E L N K L L S G V T I A A G G V L P N I Q A V L L P K K N D K G Q K K
macroH2A M S G - - - R G K S K A Q R V S I S T R **A G T I F P V S R** I R R Y L K - G C T H H Q R I A V G A P I Y Q A A V M E Y L S A E I L E L A G N A A R D N K R T R I T P R H I L L A V A N D E E L N K L L K N V T I P A G G V M P H I Q P E L L K R K D G G K F V V P K N D A A V R A A L Q K A K N A G I Q K A K N K P K P V V K A K A P V A S K S P V K K V T T P K K K A E S K **G S D S I A V L S E K** T L F L G Q K L T I V Q G N M E S L K C D A L V H P T N A T F N T T G G V G A A L L K V G G E D L K K N I I A L H E S H G D L A Y A T A L I G E A P N L Q A K H I I H V Y S P V W G K G K A E D D L E T V V K N A L T L A D E K N L A T I A F P S I G S G V N Q F P K Q T A A Q T I L K A I S N Y F V T V V T S S L R Q I Y F V L H D M E S I G V Y S L E L A R L E T S E N K
H2A.X.1 M S G R G K G G K S K A K A K S R **S S R A G L Q F P V G R** I H R F L R - R G H Y A N R V G S G A P V Y L A A V L E Y L S A E I L E L A G N A A R D N K K A R I I P R **H L Q L A V R** N D E E L N K L L S G V T I A A G G V L P N I Q A V L L P K K T T K G K S S Q S Q E Y
H2A.X.2 M S G K G K G K G H L I H H K N R R T R S Q M **A G V Q F P V G R** L H R M L K - K G H Y A D R I G S G A P V Y L A A V L E Y L T A E I L E L A G N A A R D N K R I R I V P R H L S L A I R N D E E L N D L L K G V T I A E G G V L P N I Q S A L L P K K S M K S S S K D G V Q S Q A Y
H2A.Z M A G G K A G K D S K P K T K S T S R S A R **A G L Q F P V G R** I H R Y L K S R S T N K G R V G A T A A V Y S A A I L E Y L T A E V L E L A G N A S K D L K V K R I S P R **H L Q L A I R G** D E E L D L L I K - **A T I A G G G V I P H I H K** S L I G K K G A K P T
H2B.1 M S D A A A K G G K Q A P K V A K K G E K R A G K K G G - - K I G G T G E K K R K K R K E S Y A I Y I Y N V L K **Q V H P D V G V S S K** A M S I M N S F V N D I F E R I A S E A S R L A L Q N K K S T I S S R **E I Q T A V R L L L P G E L A K** H A V S E G T K A V T K Y T S S K
H2B.3 M A G S P R K G S P - - - - K K A S S R A A S P K R A A S P K R G G S P K R G G S P A K K G K A I K K A G K R K T N K K A T T K R R R S R **R E S Y G M Y I Y K V L K Q V H P D V G I S S K** A M S I M N S F V N D I F E R L A G E A S K L A H H N K L R T I S S R E V Q T S V R **L L L P G E L A K** H A V S E G T K A V T K Y T S S R
H2B.4 M A G S P R K G S P R K G S P K K A S S R A A S P K R A A S P K R G G S P K R G R S P A K K G K A I K K A G K R K T N K K G T T K R R R S R **R E S Y G M Y I Y K V L K Q V H P D V G I S S K** A M S I M N S F V N D I F E R I A G E A S K L A H H N K L R T I S S R E V Q T S V R **L L L P G E L A K** H A V S E G T K A V T K Y T S S R
H2B.2 M S H S N K V L L Q L K V F V H D F V D M A S D K T L K R K V I T N K R V Q K K P R K R K E S Y S T Y I Y K I L K Q V H P D V G M S N E S M K I M N S F V L D V F D R I A G E A Q K L A A D N N S Q T V S A K E I Q T A V T L L L P G E L A R H A V S E G T K A V S K Y K M S K
H2B.5 M A S P R K G S P - - - - K K G S P K K T S R A A S P K R G - S P K K G - - - - K G M A A K K G G V R K G A K K N A T K R R R S R **R E S Y G I Y I Y K V L K Q V H P D V G I S S K** A M N I M N S F V N D I F E R L A G E A S R L A H H N K K Q T I A S R E V Q T S V R **L L L P G E L A K** H A V S E G T K A V T K Y T S S K
H2B.6 M A S P R K G S P R K G S P K K G S P K K T S R A A S P K R G - S P K K G - - - - K G M A A K K G G V R K G A K K N A T K R R R S R **R E S Y G I Y I Y K V L K Q V H P D V G I S S K** A M N I M N S F V N D I F E R L A G E A S R L A H H N K K Q T I A S R E V Q T S V R **L L L P G E L A K** H A V S E G T K A V T K Y T S S K
H3.1 M A R T K Q T A R K S T G G K A P R K Q L A T K A A R K S A P A T G G - - - - - V K K P H R Y **R P G T V A L R** E I R R **Y Q K S T E L L I R K L P F Q R** L V R **E I A Q D F K T D L R** F Q S T A V M A L Q E A S E A Y L V G L F E D T N L C A I H A K R V T I M P K D I Q L A R R I R G E R A
H3.3.1/2 M A R T K Q T A R K S T G G K A P R K Q L A T K A A R K S A P S T G G - - - - - V K K P H R Y **R P G T V A L R** E I R R **Y Q K S T E L L I R K L P F Q R** L V R **E I A Q D F K T D L R** F Q S A A I G A L Q E A A E A Y L V G L F E D T N L C A I H A K R V T I M P K D I Q L A R R I R G E R A
CENP-A M V K T K T T K S P R T L K K A M K S P V V T S T P M T G K G N K R R R L S S G G R E S T D E E T P K R R R T H P G T R A L K E I R F Y Q R **S T H F L I P K** L S F C R L V K E T I N K S A Y R Q D F R I Q S K A L E A L Q E A A E A F L I R F L E D T N L C A I H A R R V T I F P K D M N L V K M L K H E Q L F N A L E E
H4.1 M S G R G K G G K G L G K G G A K R H R K **I L R D N I Q G I T K P A I R R** L A R R G G V K **R I S G L I Y E E T R** G V L K V **F L E N V I R D A V T Y T E H A K R K** **T V T A M D V V Y A L K** R Q G R T L Y G F G G

- peptide identifying H2A.X.2/H2A.Z
- unique peptides
- peptides identifying the specific sub-groups H2B.3/4 and H2B.5/6
- peptides identifying H3/H3.3s
- H => uniquely identified
- H => uniquely grouped
- H => no identified by mass-spec